

Chemical Examination of *Hylocerus undatus*

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The plant material for this investigation was collected locally. The air dried, powdered plant (2 kg.) was percolated exhaustively with alcohol (10 litres). The concentrate was partitioned between 70% alcohol and petroleum ether. The petroleum ether layer was separated and concentrated. The green viscous residue (15 gms.) was chromatographed over alumina. Elution with petroleum ether gave a crystalline fraction I while elution with benzene-chloroform (1:1) gave a second crystalline fraction II. Fraction I crystallised from acetone, m.p. 68° was identified as hentriacontane through a mixed m.p. determination with an authentic sample (Found C, 84.82; H, 15.18. $C_{31}H_{64}$ requires C, 85.33; H, 14.60). Fraction II crystallised from acetone-methanol, m.p. 136° (α)_D-30° (CHCl₃) responded to Lieberman-Burchard test. The acetylated product was crystallised from acetone, m.p. 130° (α)_D-40° (CHCl₃). (Found C, 81.41; H, 11.56. $C_{31}H_{52}O_2$ requires C, 81.57; H, 11.40). The mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of the acetate of β -sitosterol remained unchanged.

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